

First Record of *Crataegus Azarolus* Var. *Aronia* L. (Rosaceae) in Libya

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 28 April 2025	<i>Crataegus azarolus</i> var. <i>aronia</i> L. (Rosaceae) is a native taxon of the Mediterranean basin, and this is the first time it has been found in Libyan territory. It grew in a silty habitat alongside other mesophyte plants about 40 km east of Almarj city. The records date from December 2017 to March 2018. Collecting this taxon from this area in east Libya, expands the known geographical distribution of <i>Crataegus azarolus</i> var. <i>aronia</i> and underscores the importance of continued botanical exploration across all regions.
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I. INTRODUCTION

The Rosaceae is a large plant family comprising over 100 genera and 2000 species [1]. *Crataegus* includes 223 accepted species [2]. Modern taxonomic classifications of the genus have been proposed by Phipps (1983) [3] and Phipps et al. (2003) [4], which has been very important source of characters that has been used to recognize species in *Crataegus* including the morphological data [3, 6,7, 8, 9, 10]. Phipps (1983) [3] reorganized the infrageneric classification and proposed 39 sections for the genus worldwide.

Commonly, *Crataegus* is taxonomically considered as difficult taxonomic group due to its remarkable morphological variation [11].

Natively, *Crataegus* occurs in Europe, North Africa, North America, North and Middle Asia and the Middle East [2]. Up to now, only *C. pallasii* Griseb, *C. laevigata* (Poir.) DC. and *C. mexicana* Moc. are reported from Libya [1].

Indeed, the flora of Libya is not completely known yet and several new plant records have been annually published [e.g. 12, 13, 14].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant specimens were first collected from the Battah area (32° 40' 47" N, 21° 06' 18" E, 372 m a.s.l.), about forty Kilometres east of Almarj city (Fig. 1a). This species was found during a vegetation analysis project in December 2017 and March 2018. The collected samples were first checked according to the Flora of Libya [1]. Moreover, further taxonomic investigations were done in the Cyrenaica Herbarium (CHUG) based on Flora of Egypt [15, 16] and Flora of Turkey [17]. Plant specimens were deposited in the Cyrenaica Herbarium (CHUG), Department of Botany, Faculty of Sciences, University of Benghazi.

III. RESULTS

Crataegus azarolus var. *aronia* L. Sp. Pl. 1: 477. 1753 [1 May 1753]

A. Taxonomy

Crataegus azarolus L. belong to the section *Crataegus* [18]. The distinguishing characteristics of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* L., when compared to other infraspecific taxa of *C. azarolus* L., include inflorescences and leaves longer than 15 mm, leaf lobes that are 1–2 times wide, and sinuses that constitute 1/2 to 1/3 of the lamina, according to Donmez and Ozderin (2019) [19].

B. General Distribution

Crataegus is native to Europe, North Africa, North America, Central Asia, and the Middle East [2]. *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* L. is a taxon found in Algeria, Spain, Iran, Lebanon, Syria, Palestine, and Turkey [2] (Fig. 1). The occurrence in Libya was expected since this taxon is known from some neighbouring territories [2].

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* L.

(Source: <https://www.gbif.org/species/8344757>, 2025).

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C. Improvement of Descriptions

Mesophyte tree, 3-5m tall, perennial, deciduous; tap root; stem aerial, cylindrical, solid, erect, with spines. Leaves are alternate, simple, exstipulate, petiolate, and obovate, measuring 4.1-5 × 2.6-3.4 cm. Leaf apex: mucronulate; leaf base: acuminate (7-9mm), with some leaves having an acute base. Leaf margin: pinnately cleft with 3-5 serrulate lobes; leaf venation: pinnately netted and sparsely tomentose. Petiole is subcircular, measuring 6-12 × 1 mm, with an attachment point width of 1.5-2 mm. Inflorescence is lateral, sometimes terminal, bracteate, with alternate flowers arranged in racemes. Flowers are pedicellate, with a short pedicel measuring 3-3.5 mm long and a longer pedicel between 12-15 mm, complete and actinomorphic. Bracts are deciduous, scaly, and oblong, measuring 3.3- 4.5 × 1-1.5 mm. Calyx: persistent, measuring 7-8 × 6-7 mm, synsepalous and toothed, with 5 deltoid lobes measuring 1.5 × 2.5 mm and an acute apex. Corolla: rotate, polypetalous, with 5 white petals, each round and measuring 5×5 mm. Androecium: polyandrous, consisting of 15 episepalous Stamens, featuring filaments measuring 4 mm and anthers measuring 1 mm, dorsifixed and versatile. Gynoecium: hypogynous and dicarpous, with style attachment at terminal, measuring 2.5 mm, and stigma type: 2 discoid, measuring 1.5 mm. Fruit types: pome, red, sometimes yellow, and black when dry, spherical to slightly prolate, measuring 12-20 × 11-18 mm, with a stalk measuring 6-19 × 1-1.7 mm. Fruit calyx teeth are equal, deltoid, measuring 1.5-2.2 × 2-2.5 mm, with the style remainder at 3-4mm and 1.5mm remaining. Seeds: 2, equal, sometimes 3, subequal, measuring (5) 7-9.5 × 3-5 mm, all together forming a spherical shape measuring (5) 7-9.5 × 6-9 mm, light yellowish-brown (beige colour) (Figs. 2, 3 & 4).

Figure 2. Influences shape and colour of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* L. (Photo by H. Eltaguri).

D. Site and Climate Description

It was discovered growing in a typical silty habitat in the field among other mesophyte plants, located about 10 km south of the shoreline and 40 km northeast of Almarj city (Fig. 5). The climate in this area is primarily Mediterranean, characterised

by very dry summers (June-August) and relatively wet winters (November-April). The highest mean monthly rainfall does not exceed 65 mm, typically occurring in December and January. The mean annual rainfall over the last two decades is around 350 mm, although it is spatially erratic. The mean maximum monthly temperature reaches 41°C in June and decreases to 21°C in January. The lowest mean minimum monthly temperature is recorded in January and December at 6°C and 7°C, respectively [20].

Arabic name: Alzarror, English name: Azarole.

Figure 3. Fruits and seeds of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* L. collected from the site (Photo by H. Eltaguri).

Figure 4. Stem spine shape of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* L. collected from the site (Photo by H. Eltaguri).

Figure 5. The location of the site (Batta) in the northeast of Libya.

IV. DISCUSSION

Finding *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* in Libya represents a significant contribution to the region's flora. This discovery aligns with previous studies that have emphasised the ongoing identification of new plant records in Libya [12, 13, 14]. Collecting this taxon from the Battah area, approximately 40 km northeast of Almarj city, expands the known geographical distribution of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* and underscores the importance of continued botanical exploration across all regions.

The morphological characteristics of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* obtained in this study, such as inflorescences and leaves longer than 15 mm, leaf lobes that are 1–2 times wide, and sinuses that are half to one-third of the lamina, are consistent with the descriptions provided by Donmez and Ozderin (2019)[19]. These traits set it apart from other infraspecific taxa of *Crataegus*. The detailed morphological description provided in this study, which includes the structure of the leaves, flowers, and fruits, contributes to the taxonomic understanding of this variety and offers a reference for future identifications. The presence of spines, a characteristic feature of the genus *Crataegus*, further supports its classification within this taxonomically challenging group [11].

The geographical distribution of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* in regions such as Algeria, Spain, Iran, Lebanon, Syria, Palestine, and Turkey [2] suggests that its occurrence in Libya is quite expected. However, this new record confirms its presence in Libya and highlights the ecological connectivity between Libya and other Mediterranean territories. The Mediterranean climate in the area where the species has been found is characterized by dry summers and wet winters, providing a suitable habitat for this mesophytic species. The finding of *C. azarolus* var. *aronia* in a silty habitat among other mesophyte plants confirms its adaptation to Mediterranean environmental conditions.

This finding contributes to the growing body of knowledge about Libya's flora and highlights the need for comprehensive botanical surveys to document a complete plant diversity assessment. The deposition of plant specimens in the Cyrenaica Herbarium (CHUG) ensures that this record is preserved for future reference and research. Identifying *C. azarolus* var. *aronia* in Libya also raises questions about its ecological role and potential uses. For example, species within the genus *Crataegus* are often appreciated for their medicinal properties, and further research could explore the potential benefits of this variety [20].

Future studies should focus on the genetic diversity and phylogenetic relationships of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* in Libya, comparing it to populations throughout the region. Additionally, molecular analyses could provide insights into its evolutionary history and dispersal patterns. Furthermore, ecological studies could explore its interactions with other plant species and its role in the local ecosystem. The new record of this taxon underscores the importance of conserving

Libya's unique habitats, especially in light of climate change and habitat degradation, which are critical concerns.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The identification of *Crataegus azarolus* var. *aronia* in Libya signifies a valuable addition to the country's Flora and enhances the broader understanding of the genus *Crataegus*. This discovery highlights the importance of ongoing botanical exploration and taxonomic research in understudied regions and the necessity of conservation efforts to protect Libya's unique plant diversity.

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